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Innovative Natural Resource Management: Conservation and Sustainability

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ABSTRACT

Industrialization is one of the best things that has happened to human existence. When counting that aspect of growth and development, it is pertinent to note that it has its disadvantages. Recent society has continued to develop technologies at a brisk pace, while this has given rise to economic growth and development, it has also given rise to environmental problems; therefore, the interrelation between technological and natural resources is a critical factor in maintaining life on the planet earth ecosystem. The world population is fast increasing, giving rise to city expansion and urban development hence, the pressure on the demand for natural resources has increased significantly and this creates an increasing importance for ideas that seek to intertwine the advancement of technology with natural resource management and sustainability. In recent times, the world's forest ecosystems such as terrestrial wildlife, wetlands, rivers, marine species, oceans and other natural resources have distorting under the pressure of human demands and the effects of climate change. When left unregulated or poorly managed, these threats can critically undermine the benefits or services, that our natural resources generate which our survival is largely dependent on. Given these pressing issues surrounding natural resource management, technology seems to be the closest solution that has availed methods and procedures for lowering the effects of environmental impairment and advancing sustainable development. This involves precision agriculture, smart city development, recycling technology, and renewable energy systems among others; all, revealing how technological inputs influence the utilization of natural resources. For instance, precision agriculture uses big data, soil sensors and aerial imagery to increase the production of crops while minimising water and chemicals usage. Green economic growth implies a transformative approach to economic development that is sustainable, and social well-being alongside conventional indicators of economic advancement (Guangwei L. & Kaipeng L. 2024). It is therefore of great importance at this point to maximise every technological innovation in natural resources management.

Keywords: natural resources management, technological innovation, economic advancement

INTRODUCTION

Technology has advanced such that it covers all fields, as such; it has become a sizable approach to solving modern problems. Whether in sciences, engineering, medicine, the internet of things or the environment, technology offers a flexible solution for complex modern issues created by human activities. The advancement of technology has birthed innovative convenience in socioeconomic growth and a healthier environment. For instance, non-conventional sources of energy including solar, wind, and hydroelectric power are transforming the energy industry by reducing the impact of conventional energy sources like coal and decreasing the emission of greenhouse gasses.

Through technological innovations, disposal of waste has improved; today unlike before, waste disposal is now a subsequent cycle of activities which transforms waste into useful resources. Technology is continuing to play major roles in renewable energy systems, precision agriculture, smart city development, and natural resource management and waste recycling among many others; all have revealed how technological inputs influence the maximisation of natural resources. The importance of technological innovation in natural resource management cannot be overemphasised, with the interrelationships between technology and natural resource management; methods and procedures for lowering the effects of natural resource impairment and advancing sustainability are being established for a healthier natural resource ecosystem.

Looking at the impact of technological innovations across fields, it is certain that technology is a driving tool for natural resource management. The path to achieving standard natural resources management and sustainability lies in effective collaboration at all levels, people engagement in innovation, stewardship and accountability as natural resource management is critical to ensuring that resources are effectively and sustainably managed. GIS technologies and remote sensing provide a platform through which the manager/government can compile information and informative data to improve decision-making for sustainable development.

What are natural resources?

Natural resources are naturally occurring materials that are useful to man or could be useful under conceivable technological, economic or social circumstances or supplies drawn from the earth, supplies such as food, building and clothing materials, fertilizers, metals, water and geothermal power. For a long time, natural resources were the domain of the natural sciences. There are 2 types of natural resources; **Renewable:** resources that are available in infinite quantities and can be used repeatedly are called renewable resources. Example: Forest, wind, water, etc. **NonRenewable:** resources that are limited in abundance due to their non-renewable nature and whose availability may run out in the future are called non-renewable resources. Examples include fossil fuels, minerals, etc.

Technology in natural resource management

Technology is an important tool for natural resource management conserves resources, minimises waste, and improves the sustainability of our environment through; **Data collection:** Technologies like GIS and remote sensing are used to gather data for natural resources management and policy decision making. **Monitoring:** Technology can be used to monitor consumption patterns to help predict shortages and minimise waste. **Resource optimisation:** precision agriculture and smart grid systems help to optimise resource use and reduce waste for farmers. **Renewable energy:** Renewable energy technologies like solar and wind power are effective fossil fuel alternatives. **Smart recycling:** promotes a circular economy where resources are recycled and put to good use. **Community engagement:** This enables community engagement through digital solutions; community engagements can help engage communities in conservation efforts. **Decision making:** Digital solutions inform real-time decision-making. Technology indeed plays a vast role in natural resource management. Below are other roles technology plays in natural resource management.

- Ground-penetrating radar
- GPS tracking
- 3D printing
- Artificial intelligence (AI)
- The Internet of Things (IoT)
- Portable X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy
- Quantum computing
- Mid-infrared spectroscopy

Technology has long been an important management tool used to preserve natural resources. Many technologies have been developed over the years to suit various needs. In some cases, management practices have been perfected and adapted to suit specific environmental and resource issues (Ellipsis drive).

Exploring applications of technological innovation in natural resource management

Healthy ecosystems provide food, medicine and timber, regulate our climate, improve our water and air quality, and protect us from natural hazards. They are also critical to our livelihoods, particularly in low and middle-income countries (LMICs). Close to 1.6 billion people – over 25 per cent of the world's population – rely on forest resources for their livelihoods, 3 billion livelihoods depend on marine and coastal biodiversity, and 150 million people living in poverty count wildlife as a valuable livelihood asset. In addition to undermining most international environmental goals, current trends in biodiversity and ecosystem loss threaten 80 per cent of the UN Sustainable Development Goals' targets related to poverty, hunger, health, water, cities, climate, oceans and land. We must protect these fragile and constantly changing systems, both for the sustainable development of cities and for the future of the planet (UNDP Singapore, 2020) With the rapid increase of the world's population and continuous city expansion, the pressure on the demand for resources increases significantly and this creates increasing importance for ideas that seek to intertwine the advancement of technology with sustainability (Automate.org)

Application of Geographical Information System (GIS) in natural resource management

GIS is a mapping process and functions as a way of collecting, storing, manipulating, analysing, organising, managing, summarising, and displaying various types of geographical data. Its applications extend to several industries, including natural resource management. GIS is a powerful tool in natural resource management as it helps to support effective and sustainable decision-making by improving the amount and type of data available to policymakers and decision-makers. Proper management of our natural resources is critical as it impacts everyone.

The following are ways GIS applies to natural resource management.

Data collection: GIS and remote sensing are technological tools that are widely used in mapping for data collection and analysis in natural resource management. Whether it is vegetation maps, shoreline erosion maps, land cover maps, saltwater marsh migration maps or soil maps, when a variety of data needs to be collected and analysed before the maps are developed, this is where remote sensing technology applies. The integration of remote sensing with topographical maps maximises its effectiveness in showing the variations in climates, soil and other factors. Aerial photographs (vertical or oblique) help collect spatial data in the same location within intervals (hours, days, seasons, years) depending on the topography of the area. Satellite photographs can also be used and are significantly better as they have higher spectral, spatial, radiometric, and temporal resolutions and are more detailed.

Monitor Environmental Changes: GIS has many applications, and utilising it to monitor land area changes between periods helps to improve decision-making and track changes in the environment due to climate and human impact. Remote sensing, satellite imagery, and aerial photography are valuable for monitoring deforestation assessment, land change, urbanisation, habitat fragmentation, salt marsh monitoring, and coastal shoreline erosion. Natural resource management uses GIS data to study and monitor changes to help improve decision-making (Darius M, 2022).

Monitoring the Environment

The Geographical Information System is a viable tool for monitoring the growth and decline of natural resources in the environment. It helps to determine qualitative and quantitative data regarding environmental issues like soil erosion, land degradation, pollution, etc. Natural resource management officials can maximise the effectiveness of GIS in real-time monitoring of ecological conditions.

Monitor Environmental Changes

GIS has vast applications, it can be used in monitoring land area changes between periods to inform, improve decision-making and track changes in the environment due to human and climate impact in real-time. Satellite imagery, remote sensing, and aerial photography are essential for monitoring and change, deforestation assessment, urbanisation, habitat fragmentation, coastal shoreline erosion and salt marsh monitoring. The application of GIS data to study and monitor changes in natural resource management helps in improving decision-making.

Natural Hazards and Risk Assessment

GIS as a technological tool helps to monitor possible risks and hazardous areas prone to flooding, landslides, earthquakes, forest fires, droughts, soil erosion, and more. Owing to the massive population growth and high pace of development spreads, it is critical to attempt to mitigate risks through early planning and preparations. Natural resource management organisations analyse, organise, manage and monitor natural or human-created hazards that have occurred previously or have the potential to reoccur with the help of spatial data from GIS.

Natural Resource Inventory Monitoring

Application of GIS Data in Forest Management: Forests are generally viewed as a renewable resource; however. Deforestation can happen quickly, such as when a fire sweeps through the landscape or the forest is clear-cut to make way for an oil palm plantation. While deforestation appears to be declining in some countries, it remains disturbingly high in others—including Brazil and the Democratic

Republic of the Congo (worldwildlife.org). Forest managers can use GIS data to monitor forest cover, forest types, and human encroachment into a forest or land/protected area, and more. GIS is critical in developing forest management plans, decisions, and policy-making to ensure that forest resources are protected and utilised sustainably.

Application of GIS Data in Watershed Management: GIS plays a critical role in watershed management. Water management is an ongoing challenge, and satellite data helps monitor water bodies such as lakes, rivers, dams, and reservoirs mapped in 3D and monitored using GIS technology (Darius M. 2022).

Application of GIS Data to Combat Desertification: Desertification occurs when land in arid, semi-arid, and dry semi-humid areas becomes degraded and loses its ability to support biological productivity. It can range from slight to severe, with moderate desertification causing at least a 10–25% drop in agricultural productivity. GIS data helps determine soil types, nutrient availability, the best land use practices within a particular area, and their impacts on the environment. GIS data can also determine slope information and if desert-like conditions are encroaching in the area.

Application of GIS Data in Biodiversity Management: GIS data aids land management of flora and fauna within protected areas and monitors invasive species' presence and distribution using aerial, ground, and satellite photographs. This information also helps to determine the amount of cover and food present, especially for herbivores during certain times of the year (Darius M. 2022).

Monitoring Pollution

“Sensing technologies are the new eyes and ears for cities to understand air quality, as well as the sources and health risks from pollution. We have a unique opportunity to work with technology innovators, academia, the private sector and civil society to connect health and technology to truly clean the air we breathe.” Dr Claudia Sheinbaum.

In some parts of the world, a lack of data makes understanding local pollution—and its impact on community health—nearly impossible. New, lower-cost air pollution sensing technologies can change that. These new sensors are not only more accessible than traditional monitoring methods.

They also show how pollution changes from neighbourhood to neighbourhood, or even block to block. This kind of hyperlocal data can shine a light on previously invisible hotspots, helping officials and empowering communities to make a stronger case for changes that protect public health and the environment (globalcleanair.org).

With the help of a machine learning algorithm, local authorities can predict the level of pollution 24 to 48 hours prior. This can be achieved by mobile networks from weather, pollution, and traffic sensors.

Technological innovations in resource optimisation

Agricultural technology, also known as “agrotech,” encompasses a broad range of disciplines and devices that improve agricultural output. That includes vehicles, robotics, computers, satellites, drones, mobile devices, and software. The use of big data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) technology in agriculture is also an example of how the farming sector is embracing technological advancement. Changes in farming and field management during the past few decades have been revolutionary. The employment of modern, state-of-the-art technology in agriculture can be credited with much of the recent success in crop management and increased harvests (eos.com).

Precision agriculture: this is a data-driven approach to managing crops that uses advanced technologies to improve productivity and sustainability. It involves collecting, analyzing, and applying data using technologies like remote sensing, unmanned aerial vehicles, artificial intelligence, the Internet of things and cloud computing to make more efficient decisions at every stage of production. Precision agriculture can help to achieve the following:

- **Improve soil quality:** Understand local soil types and improve soil quality
- **Manage resources:** Reduce the need for water, fertilizers, and pesticides
- **Reduce environmental impact:** Reduce the environmental footprint of farming
- **Mitigate climate change:** Reduce the sector's vulnerability to climate change

- **Monitor pests and diseases:** Monitor and diagnose pests, diseases, and extreme weather events early
- **Conserve water:** Use variable rate irrigation (VRI) to conserve water resources.

Technology for waste material recycling

Waste generation and disposal are major challenges faced by mankind in this century. The management of the huge amounts of waste generated from domestic and industrial activities has continued to be a source of concern for humanity globally because of its impact on the ecosystem and human health. Waste generated by households, industry, schools, restaurants, farms, and, indeed, all human activities require proper management and disposal. Global waste generation, which was 2.02 billion tons in 2016, is projected to reach 2.59 billion tons in 2030 and 3.4 billion tons in 2050. The rate of waste generation has been predicted to overtake the population growth rate by more than double during the same period (Awogbemi et al, 2022).

Waste generation by region in 2016, 2030, and 2050 (millions of tons). Source: mdpi.com

Waste recycling and reuse in manufacturing

Waste recycling and reuse is a viable way to minimise, reduce waste, and manage waste. Most of the items that are discarded as waste can be recycled and reused. Waste recycling and reuse reduce the number of wastes sent to landfills and incinerators, ensure the conservation of natural resources, save energy, reduce pollution and contamination, and support the manufacturing sector. Recycling of wastes from the manufacturing sector minimises the use of new raw materials, reduces the environmental impact of waste treatment and disposal, saves money, and ensures that minimum energy is consumed during product manufacturing. For sustainable waste recycling systems, the waste generated must be collected, sorted, processed, and converted to other usable items. Consumers are to be encouraged to patronize items produced from recycled materials. Items such as paper, paper and cardboard, food, plastics, metals, rubber, leather and textiles, wood, stones and brick, ceramics, and glass are the common wastes that can be recycled and reused.

Metal scraps can be converted into nails, aluminum cans, and other steel products, waste papers can be transformed into egg cartons, cereal boxes, paper towels, newspapers, laundry detergent bottles, glass containers, etc. All these materials are made from recycled waste.

Zero waste manufacturing, improved waste management, inappropriate waste disposal, open dumping of waste, and landfilling pollutes natural habitats (air, land, and water) and exacerbate health-related

problems. Greenhouse gases such as carbon monoxide and methane generated from the refuse heaps at dumpsites promote air pollution, whereas the leachate formed in the landfills contaminates ground and surface water sources. Proper waste management strategies including waste prevention, minimization, remediation, and re-utilisation can help solve many avoidable problems and safeguard the ecosystem. Zero waste manufacturing (ZWM) entails the various techniques that promote a manufacturing system that utilises minimum materials, generates minimum wastes, and encourages waste re-utilisation. Though wastes cannot be completely prevented in manufacturing processes, strategies that allow waste prevention, minimisation, recycling, redesigning, and re-use contribute towards ZWM processes. Waste generated from manufacturing can be substantially reduced by the adoption of methodologies that allow a product to be used for other applications after becoming obsolete or undesirable for its primary application. This means creating a product with multi-utility capability and a dependable service life across multiple utilisation cycles is a way to achieve ZW in the manufacturing sector. Additionally, conventional manufacturing processing poses a great challenge to the concept of sustainable material utilisation, lean material production, and minimum material removal during production. To achieve ZWM, innovative manufacturing techniques and pathways must be adopted and utilised (Awogbemi et al, 2022).

ZWM is a crucial aspect of natural resource management. It does not mean absolute zero waste as waste is almost inevitable but waste minimisation to the barest minimum is achievable, and to foster a standard natural resource management, waste management is key to preserving and protecting both our environment and our natural resources ecosystem. To establish this, necessary legislation, policies, and programs must be standardised and dutifully implemented. A uniform, comprehensive and all-encompassing strategy with specific timelines must guide all stakeholders. This will mean grassroots mobilisation and education geared towards behavioural change for citizens. The people must buy into and wholeheartedly support sustainable consumption since the adverse effects of unmanaged waste on global climate change and human health are absolute and evident. Many people and communities are unwilling to imbibe sustainable behaviour and lifestyles that will mitigate the raging effects of environmental degradation, this is why Governments at various levels must be willing to invest in sensitisation, education, training, regulation, and research on innovative ways to achieve ZWM.

Importance of natural resource management

Natural resource management is important for many reasons, which include;

Protecting the environment: proper management of natural resources will help to prevent environmental damage and pollution, which can harm human health and ecosystems. Everything we use today, every exchange of energy and comfort on earth; home, food, clothing, automobiles, roads, electricity, books, furniture, cooking gas, utensils, toys, medicine etc. – originates from natural resources. A large amount of the energy we consume today comes from non-renewable sources. Which entails that they are irreplaceable after usage. Fossil fuels, which are the primary source of energy in recent times, take millions of years to form and are the most significant source of non-renewable energy used widely. Managing these resources well will guarantee their rational usage. It will also limit the degradation it causes to the environment. For instance, the use of resources in various ways produces a lot of waste, which, in some places, is disposed of into the water bodies. This action pollutes rivers and lakes and affects biodiversity. Proper management and regulation of natural resources will minimise waste generation, reduce environmental pollution for healthier living, and prevent biodiversity loss.

Conserving resources: Managing natural resources helps ensure environmental sustainability such that future generations have access to the same resources that we do today (vitality.io).

Maintaining balance in the ecosystem: All parts of the environment are connected, and over-consuming natural resources can disrupt this balance.

Promoting economic stability: Sustainable resource management can promote economic stability. Overexploitation of natural resources can have a significant impact on the environment and human health. It leads to deforestation, soil erosion, air pollution, water contamination, and loss of biodiversity. This in turn affects climate change and increases the risk of floods, droughts and other extreme weather

events that could be harmful to normal functioning of the ecosystem which in turn affects socio-economic growth.

Ensuring social equity: Sustainable resource management can help ensure social equity.

CONCLUSION

It is evident from the studies above that technology plays a major role in natural resource management. However, care must be taken to minimise the negative impact of technology on natural resource management through government initiatives like citizen education, sensitisation, inclusion in decision making and proper engagement of local stakeholders. While advanced technology is playing important roles in natural resource management and sustainability from preserving the forest for a balanced and healthy ecosystem to providing food through improved agrotech and waste management through recycling and reuse, policies and regulations must also be put in place to ensure long-term benefits. The government must enable collaboration for individuals, and stakeholders both local and international who wish to invest in natural resource management through technological innovations and ensure they are properly regulated for sustainability. In conclusion, technological innovations offer tremendous potential in improving natural resource management and addressing some of the world's most pressing environmental challenges. By embracing advanced technologies, fostering collaboration, and ensuring inclusive and sustainable practices, we can work towards a more resilient and sustainable future for natural resource management globally.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Green economic growth implies a transformative approach to economic development and management practices that is sustainable. Creating a stable and sustainable natural resource management considering the increase in demand for natural resource utilisation due to increasing world population, urbanisation industrialization and climate change requires a collective effort. Government must collaborate with stakeholders at all levels and invest in natural resource management to safeguard natural resource reserves. A measure of accountability but be put in place to ensure compliance. To ensure the sustainability of our natural resources and the health of ecosystems, the following steps are necessary;

1. Investment in Advanced Data Collection and Monitoring Technologies Technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), remote sensing, and satellite imagery have revolutionized the way natural resources are monitored and managed. These tools provide real-time data on resource distribution, health, and changes over time, enabling more accurate decision-making. Governments and organizations should invest in expanding the use of these technologies to improve resource management and ensure more efficient monitoring of land, water, and biodiversity.
2. Implement Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Predictive Analysis AI and machine learning algorithms can be harnessed to predict future trends in resource availability, identify potential threats to ecosystems, and optimize resource allocation. By analyzing large sets of environmental data, AI can forecast natural resource depletion, climate impacts, and ecosystem changes, helping managers implement proactive, rather than reactive, strategies.
3. Promote Circular Economy Solutions Technologies that facilitate the circular economy—such as resource recycling, waste-to-energy technologies, and sustainable production practices—should be adopted to reduce resource consumption and minimise waste. Businesses and governments can collaborate to incentivise industries to adopt cleaner, more sustainable practices using these technological solutions to achieve zero-waste objectives and promote sustainability in the long run.
4. Support the Use of Blockchain for Transparency and Accountability Blockchain technology can enhance transparency and accountability in natural resource management. By creating secure, decentralised systems for tracking the sourcing, distribution, and usage of resources, blockchain can reduce illegal activities, such as poaching or illegal logging, and ensure fair and equitable distribution of resources, particularly in developing nations.

5. Enhance Public-Private Partnerships for Innovation Collaboration between governments, NGOs, and private tech companies will help to drive innovation in natural resource management. Public-private partnerships can fund research and development for emerging technologies, such as precision agriculture, water purification, and renewable energy solutions, that promote sustainable resource use. These partnerships can also help scale successful technologies globally, particularly in underserved areas.
6. Invest in Education and Capacity Building To fully maximise the potential of technological innovations, emphasis must be on grassroots training and education of resource managers, policymakers, and local communities. Building the capacity to understand and effectively use these technologies ensures that they are implemented efficiently and ethically, helping stakeholders at all levels to make informed decisions.
7. Prioritise Ecological and Social Sustainability While technological innovations can offer significant benefits in terms of resource management, they must be implemented in ways that prioritise ecological and social safety and sustainability. Technology design and implementation must be regulated to ensure that the use complements and supports sustainable practices that protect biodiversity, ensure social equity, and foster community involvement in decision-making processes.

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